

Promoting geoinformatics in Estonian schools - experiences from the project “Cool geography lesson”

Merli Neito¹

¹ Department of Geography, University of Tartu, Tartu, Estonia

Correspondence: Merli Neito (merli.neito@ut.ee)

Abstract. The project *Cool Geography Lesson* was launched in Estonian schools in 2016 by the University of Tartu geography students’ association EGEA-Tartu. Over seven years (2016–2023), the initiative reached over 12,000 students across more than 150 schools. The project aimed to enhance secondary school students’ understanding of geography through workshops covering various topics, including geoinformatics. These workshops provided students with practical experience and real-life applications of geographic knowledge. The study presents insights from these workshops tailored for lower and upper secondary school students (ages 12–18). Examples of activities with a geoinformatics focus included creating a 3D model of Estonia’s capital city, Tallinn and generating a simple choropleth map of Estonia. This study describes the project’s structure and results, challenges in teaching GIS and feedback from participants. The results show that hands-on and interactive learning is important for teaching geoinformatics. However, challenges like low technological literacy and limited access to equipment still exist. Feedback from both students and teachers shows a strong interest in continuing this kind of workshops, which suggests that there is a real need for practical GIS education in secondary schools.

Submission Type. Project, case study

BoK Concepts. [OI2] GIS and T workforce themes

Keywords. geoinformatics education, promoting GIS, technological literacy

1 Introduction

There is an understanding that geoinformatics should be introduced earlier in formal education to build spatial

literacy and prepare students for an increasingly data-driven world (Metoyer et al., 2015). In Estonian schools, geography curriculum is traditionally structured with a strong emphasis on physical geography in both lower and upper secondary levels. Approximately two-thirds of the curriculum focuses on physical geography, while the remaining third is dedicated to human geography (Riigi Teataja 2023a, 2023b). While this framework provides a solid theoretical foundation, it offers limited opportunities for students to interact with spatial data or geoinformation tools in practical contexts. Although GIS is widely recognised for its educational potential, actual classroom implementation remains limited (Höhnle et al., 2013).

Geoinformatics was added as an elective lesson to the Estonian geography curriculum in 2011 (Roosaare et al., 2014). Although the subject is becoming more common, schools in Estonia – and in many other countries – continue to face several challenges: limited teacher training, outdated or insufficient technology, tight curriculum schedules, and unequal access to resources (Bernhäuserová et al., 2022). Teachers also report not having enough time to build GIS skills (Höhnle et al., 2011), along with weak institutional support and a lack of equipment or IT help (Roosaare & Liiber, 2013; Kidman & Palmer, 2006).

In response to these gaps, Cool Geography Lesson – a student-led outreach initiative by EGEA-Tartu – was launched in 2016. The project aimed to bridge the divide between theoretical geography education and applied spatial analysis through workshop-based learning in Estonian schools. Teachers could choose from seven workshop topics, developed by researchers and lecturers from the University of Tartu. The topics included: smartphone and location-based services, GPS orienteering, geoinformatics, physical geography (meteorology), virtual reality in landscape research, 3D modelling, and city planning. This study focuses

specifically on two workshops: Geoinformatics and 3D modelling. To participate, geography teachers signed up for their school through a registration form, booking 2–5 lessons on a single topic. All workshops were provided free of charge to schools.

2 Methodology

The project was targeted at students in lower secondary (grades 7–9) and upper secondary (grades 10–12) schools. Special emphasis was placed on reaching rural or peripheral schools that lack the resources to attend events in major cities like Tartu or Tallinn. The workshops were taught by geography students from the University of Tartu and emphasised applied learning using open-source tools such as QGIS and publicly available spatial datasets. Each session followed a consistent structure: a short theoretical introduction, followed by a practical task using geospatial tools, concluded with a small discussion and feedback collection via short questionnaires.

In the geoinformatics workshop, students created a choropleth map of wells in Estonia. They began by finding spatial and statistical data (e.g., the public dataset of Estonian wells), importing the data into QGIS, and then visualising it through mapping techniques. Students customised their maps by selecting symbology and adding standard cartographic elements such as a legend, scale bar, north arrow, and title (Fig. 1). Open data sources from national geospatial portals were also introduced.

Figure 1. Excerpt from the practical work in geoinformatics workshop.

In the 3D modelling workshop, students worked with Digital Elevation and Surface Model (DEM and DSM) and LiDAR-based point cloud data to create a three-dimensional model of Tallinn's Old Town (Fig. 2). These datasets enabled students to explore urban structure and elevation in a 3D environment, practising real-world applications in urban planning. Most students had no prior

experience with such technologies, making this exposure particularly impactful in connecting theory with practice.

Figure 2. Excerpt from the practical work in 3D lesson.

2.1 Data and Software Availability

No code was developed or used in this work and detailed data collected in the questionnaires will not be shared due to privacy constraints.

3 Results

Over seven years, more than 680 workshops were conducted in over 150 unique schools across Estonia (Fig. 3), reaching more than 12,000 students and teachers. A total of 45 geography students from the University of Tartu contributed to the project, gaining valuable teaching and outreach experience. During the project more than 230 visits were conducted, with the geoinformatics and 3D modelling workshops accounting for approximately 40 of those visits and over 120 workshops. These topics were among the most technically advanced and posed unique challenges.

Feedback from teachers and students indicated strong interest in the project. Educators appreciated the practical, real-world applications of geography that were typically absent from the curriculum. Teachers also valued the novelty and freshness of having external guests leading the class. However, several technical and pedagogical challenges emerged. Common obstacles included:

- Low digital literacy: Students often struggled with basic computer tasks, such as unpacking files or using unfamiliar interfaces.
- Hardware limitations: Computers in many schools lacked the hardware needed to process large geospatial datasets without software crashes

Figure 3. Map of all visited schools in Estonia during the project. Map by Merli Neito and Elina Maarja Suitso.

- Time constraints: The standard 45-minute lesson was insufficient for completing the workshops. A 75-minute format or two consecutive 45-minute lessons proved more effective.
- Student hesitation: Without close instructor support, students were often too shy to ask for help, leading them to fall behind. Active monitoring and encouragement were essential to maintain engagement and ensure a sense of achievement.

Recurring aspects from student feedback highlighted the importance of explaining the “why”: why the activity was relevant, why these tools mattered, and what purpose the lesson served. Students were more engaged when they understood the broader context and goals of the tasks. Technical issues such as slow program loading, software crashes, and difficulty finding tools in QGIS were also frequently reported. These challenges often slowed the progress and limited what could be achieved during a single session.

Despite these throwbacks, overall feedback of these workshops was overwhelmingly positive. Many noted that students were more curious and engaged when interacting with young instructors who brought new perspectives to the classroom. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the project faced interruptions and postponements, but the extended timeline allowed for

continued school participation once in-person visits resumed.

In 2020 the project received the Estonian Science Popularisation Grand Prize in the category "activities/series of activities" which showcases the wider acknowledgement of the project and its success.

4 Conclusion

The Cool Geography Lesson project proved to be a highly successful initiative that filled a significant gap in the practical teaching of geography in Estonian schools. Despite its popularity and positive reception, the project was unfortunately discontinued due to lack of funding in subsequent years. However, during the active project years, annual registration requests consistently exceeded the project’s capacity often by more than double. This clearly demonstrates a continued demand for such initiatives that bring real-world applications of geography into the classroom. Reviving the project would require training a new generation of university geography students and updating lesson materials to reflect current technological and educational developments. However, the foundation has been laid, and the enthusiasm from both students and educators suggests that, given the opportunity, the project would be welcomed back with open arms.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The author declares that she has used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. AI tools were used for shortening the text, improving grammar and sentence structure but not for generating scientific content, research data, or any conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the author without AI assistance.

Acknowledgements.

The project received funding for 7 years from the Estonian Research Council and Estonian Ministry of Education and Research.

The project was initiated by University of Tartu geography PhD student Laura Altin and human geography professor Rein Ahas. Laura Altin also played a central role in shaping the project, actively contributing with new ideas and developing innovative workshop topics.

References

- Bernhäuserová, V., Havelková, L., Hátlová, K., Hanus, M.: The Limits of GIS Implementation in Education: A Systematic Review, *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Informatics*, 11(12), 592, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi11120592>, 2022.
- Höhnle, S., Schubert, J. C., Uphues, R.: Barriers to GI(S) use in schools – A comparison of international empirical results, *Learning with GI 2011: : implementing digital earth in education*, 124–133, 2011.
- Höhnle, S., Schubert, J. C., Uphues, R.: What are the constraints to GIS usage? Selected results of a teacher survey about constraints in the school context, *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education*, 22(3), 226–240, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10382046.2013.817662>, 2013.
- Kidman, G., Palmer, G.: GIS: The Technology is There but the Teaching is Yet to Catch Up, *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education*, 15(3), 289–296, <https://doi.org/10.2167/irgee196i.0>, 2006.
- Metoyer, S., Bednarz, S., Bednarz, R.: Spatial Thinking in Education: Concepts, Development, and Assessment. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-4-431-55519-3_3, 2015.
- Riigi Teataja: Põhikooli riiklik õppekava. [National curriculum for lower secondary schools]. <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/129082014020?leiaKehiv>, 2023a.
- Riigi Teataja: Gümnaasiumi riiklik õppekava. [National curriculum for upper secondary schools]. <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/529042024001/consolide>, 2023b.
- Roosaare, J., Liiber, Ü.: GIS in school education in Estonia – looking for an holistic approach, *Journal of Research and Didactics in Geography*, 2, 47–56, 2013.
- Roosaare, J., Liiber, Ü., Mõisja, K.: Implementing a Geoinformatics Course for Secondary Schools: First Lessons to be Learned, *GI Forum*, 254–260, <https://doi.org/10.1553/giscience2014s254>, 2014.